

Clinical and Biochemical Profile of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) Patient in Koshi Region

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD), connected to obesity, insulin resistance, and metabolic syndrome, is a global health issue. Management requires understanding its biochemical and clinical properties in diverse geographical contexts.

Methods: Katihar Medical College in Bihar's Koshi area undertook this two-year prospective observational study. Clinical evaluations of 100 NAFLD patients included anthropometric measures, demographic information, and biochemical analyses of lipid profiles, insulin resistance indicators, inflammatory indices, liver function tests, and insulin resistance. FibroScan measured liver fibrosis non-invasively.

Results: Research indicates that male patients in the middle age group are more likely to have central obesity (BMI 29.7 kg/m², waist size 96.5 cm). Liver damage was detected through hyperlipidemia (total cholesterol 215.2 mg/dL, LDL cholesterol 145.3 mg/dL, triglycerides 175.4 mg/dL), insulin resistance (fasting glucose 110.7 mg/dL, insulin 15.3 μU/mL, HOMA-IR 4.1), and increased liver enzymes (ALT 55.3 U/L, AST 47. A high C-reactive protein of 6.5 mg/L and an average FibroScan score of 8.2 kPa suggested severe fibrosis.

Conclusion: Koshi NAFLD patients had metabolic and liver disorders, as shown in this study. The findings emphasise early detection, lifestyle changes, and coordinated management to slow disease progression and its impacts. These findings should be confirmed in bigger, multi-center trials, ethnic and regional variances investigated, and fresh therapeutic targets for personalised treatment found.

Keywords: Biochemical profile, Fibrosis, Insulin resistance, NAFLD, Obesity.

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Introduction

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD), which affects 25% of the world's population, is the most common chronic liver disease and includes Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis (NASH), which can lead to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma, and basic hepatic steatosis [1]. Increased NAFLD is connected to metabolic syndrome and global obesity. Genetic, metabolic, and environmental factors cause NAFLD. Illness is caused by insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and inflammation [2].

NAFLD is symptomless, making early diagnosis and treatment difficult. NAFLD increases the risk of heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and other metabolic problems, therefore identify and treat it early. NAFLD research in Koshi is crucial due to demography and socioeconomics. NAFLD prevalence and severity depend on genetics, nutrition, and lifestyle [3].

Lack of health information and healthcare access make it tougher to prevent and treat illness. There are numerous compelling reasons to study Koshi NAFLD biochemistry and clinical characteristics. First, it will show this group's specific sickness

traits and risk factors, which may differ from others. Identifying the biochemical and clinical indicators of NAFLD in this population to improve screening and detection. Our findings can aid regional NAFLD prevention.

Objectives

- To study Koshi NAFLD patients' demographics and health.
- To assess biochemical profiles for metabolic syndrome, lipid profiles, and liver function.
- To identify NAFLD risk factors and comorbidities in this cohort.

Overview of Existing Research on NAFLD

[4] States NAFLD is very common and hurts the liver and the body as a whole. About 20% to 30% of people in the West have this liver disease. The "two-hit" theory says that NAFLD starts with steatosis in the liver and then moves on to NASH, inflammation, fibrosis, and finally cirrhosis or hepatocellular cancer in the worst cases [5]. Weight, metabolic syndrome, dyslipidemia, and type 2 diabetes are risk factors for NAFLD,

according to [6]. Gene polymorphisms in PNPLA3 and TM6SF2 increase the risk of NAFLD and its progression, underscoring the importance of genetic predisposition. Food and exercise habits are important; sedentary lifestyle, fructose consumption, and saturated fat consumption are connected to NAFLD.

Clinical and Biochemical Characteristics of NAFLD

NAFLD is asymptomatic, especially early on, making it hard to diagnose without screening. Nonspecific symptoms include fatigue, malaise, and right upper quadrant abdominal pain [7]. NASH and cirrhosis can cause significant symptoms such as jaundice, ascites, and hepatic encephalopathy. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease is characterised by elevated liver enzymes, particularly ALT and AST. The AST/ALT ratio may grow with fibrosis; however NAFLD patients usually have a ratio below one. Besides metabolic changes, biochemical abnormalities include fasting hyperglycemia, LDL cholesterol, and triglycerides. In NAFLD patients, HOMA-IR and other insulin resistance indicators are elevated [8]. Histologically, NAFLD is either simple steatosis (fat build up in hepatocytes) or NASH (steatosis, inflammation, ballooning, and fibrosis). Liver biopsies are the most accurate way to diagnose NASH and stage fibrosis; however FibroScan and serum biomarkers are becoming more common.

Previous Studies in Similar Demographic Regions

[9] Examined NAFLD prevalence and characteristics in different demographic regions to help public health officials understand the disease burden and guide public health initiatives. NAFLD is rising in South Asian countries like India, as elsewhere.

According to [10], 16–32% of the population has NAFLD, with the highest incidence among overweight, diabetic, and metabolic syndrome patients. In a North Indian tertiary care institution, 25.4% of regular check-up patients had NAFLD. The study identified obesity and insulin resistance as key risk factors. Another South Indian study found a 32% prevalence of NAFLD and a strong link with metabolic syndrome components.

Rural Southern Indians had 9.3% NAFLD prevalence, lower than urban rates. This statistically significant result shows how lifestyle changes affect non-urban areas. NAFLD's complex genetic, environmental, and behavioural interplay is explained by regional study. Due to obesity, diabetes, and sedentary lives, urban Maharashtra inhabitants have higher incidence of NAFLD than rural residents. Koshi's demographics and socioeconomic circumstances make NAFLD's characteristics and prevalence important [11].

NAFLD patients in this area may have different clinical and biochemical profiles due to nutrition, exercise, and healthcare access.

Figure 1: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) (Source:[12])

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This two-year prospective observational study was undertaken at Katihar Medical College in Koshi, Bihar, India. The study examined biochemical and clinical features of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease patients.

Study Duration

Twenty-four months were spent on research and the lengthy study allowed for comprehensive data collection and follow-up, ensuring solid results.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients 18 years or older.
- Patients diagnosed with NAFLD based on clinical, radiological, and biochemical criteria.
- Patients had given informed consent to participate in the trial.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with significant alcohol consumption (defined as more than 20 grams per day for women and more than 30 grams per day for men).
- Patients with other causes of liver disease such as viral hepatitis (hepatitis B and C), autoimmune hepatitis, and genetic liver diseases.
- Patients on medications known to cause steatosis (e.g., corticosteroids, amiodarone).
- Patients with severe comorbid conditions that could interfere with the study outcomes.

Data Collection Methods

Each participant's clinical and biochemical data were meticulously completed. Clinical evaluations included physical exams and medical histories. We recorded gender, BMI, age, waist size, and blood pressure. We also noted the patients' diets, activity, and family history of metabolic disorders or liver disease. Fasting blood was drawn and examined for biochemical tests. These comprised liver function tests (ALT, AST, ALP, and GGT), lipid profile

(total cholesterol, HDL, LDL, and triglycerides), fasting blood glucose, insulin levels, and insulin resistance indicator HOMA-IR.

Inflammatory markers including adipokines and CRP were also examined. Transient elastography (FibroScan) and ultrasound were used to assess hepatic steatosis and fibrosis. A liver biopsy was considered to confirm the diagnosis and assess steatosis, inflammation, and fibrosis in individuals with elevated liver enzymes or suspected advanced liver disease.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS version 25.0 was used to analyse protected database data. Demographic and clinical data from the research population were summarised using descriptive statistics. Continuous data were represented by mean $\pm$ SD or median (interquartile range), whereas categorical variables were expressed by frequencies and percentages. Biochemical markers like liver enzymes, lipid profiles, and insulin resistance indicators were compared to clinical parameters like blood pressure, waist circumference, and BMI using Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients.

Statisticians explored metabolic syndrome differences in NAFLD subgroups. Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests were employed for categorical variables and independent sample t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables.

In NAFLD patients, multivariate logistic regression found independent progressive fibrosis variables. All analyses showed statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

This study examined Koshi NAFLD patients' biochemical and clinical profiles using advanced statistical analysis and rigorous data. The findings should inform NAFLD treatment and intervention in this cohort.

Results

Demographic Profile of the Patients

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Characteristic	Value
Number of Patients	100
Age (years)	45.3 $\pm$ 12.1
Gender (Male/Female)	60/40
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.7 $\pm$ 4.3
Waist Circumference (cm)	96.5 $\pm$ 10.2
Blood Pressure (mmHg)	135/85 $\pm$ 10/7

NAFLD patients in this study average 45.3 years old. There are 60% men and 40% women, with a slight male majority. Patients with a BMI of 29.7 kg/m² are often overweight, increasing their risk of NAFLD. Due to central obesity, this group has

higher metabolic difficulties (average waist size 96.5 cm). Many hypertensives had high blood pressure (135/85 mmHg), highlighting NAFLD's complexity and the need for metabolic care.

Clinical Characteristics

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics

Clinical Parameter	Mean ± SD (Range)
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.7 ± 4.3 (22.1-37.8)
Waist Circumference (cm)	96.5 ± 10.2 (75-120)
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	135 ± 10 (120-160)
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	85 ± 7 (70-100)
Hepatomegaly (n, %)	55 (55%)

Obesity and overweight are common, with a mean BMI of 29.7 kg/m². Diseases enhance NAFLD risk and progression.

A mean waist circumference of 96.5 cm shows NAFLD-related central obesity and metabolic inefficiency. This population is at risk for cardiovascular disease due to hypertension with

systolic blood pressures of 135 and diastolic of 85. Hepatomegaly in 55% of patients shows NAFLD may harm the liver. These symptoms show how NAFLD affects Koshi's metabolism and cardiovascular system.

Biochemical Profile

Table 3: Biochemical Profile

Biochemical Parameter	Mean ± SD (Range)
ALT (U/L)	55.3 ± 28.1 (20-130)
AST (U/L)	47.8 ± 22.4 (15-100)
ALP (U/L)	120.5 ± 35.7 (60-210)
GGT (U/L)	65.7 ± 30.2 (25-150)
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	215.2 ± 45.3 (150-320)
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	40.1 ± 9.5 (25-60)
LDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	145.3 ± 38.6 (90-220)
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	175.4 ± 60.3 (90-300)
Fasting Blood Glucose (mg/dL)	110.7 ± 25.1 (80-180)
Fasting Insulin (μU/mL)	15.3 ± 7.8 (5-30)
HOMA-IR	4.1 ± 2.5 (1-10)
CRP (mg/L)	6.5 ± 3.2 (2-15)
FibroScan Score (kPa)	8.2 ± 3.5 (3-16)

This study found metabolic imbalance and liver damage in NAFLD patients. Hepatic inflammation and NAFLD development are indicated by high ALT (55.3 U/L) & AST (47.8 U/L). High ALP (120.5 U/L) & GGT (65.7 U/L) show cholestasis and liver cell death, confirming hepatic involvement. Dyslipidemia, which raises cardiovascular disease risk, is characterised by high total cholesterol (215.2 mg/dL), low HDL cholesterol (40.1 mg/dL), and higher LDL cholesterol (145.3 mg/dL) and triglycerides (175.4 mg/dL). NAFLD is marked by insulin resistance, shown by higher fasting glucose (110.7 mg/dL), insulin (15.3 μU/mL), and HOMA-IR (4.1) levels. CRP (6.5 mg/L) indicates NAFLD-related systemic inflammation. FibroScan values of 8.2 kPa indicate liver fibrosis, affecting prognosis and treatment. The complicated relationship between metabolic imbalances and liver pathology in NAFLD emphasises the necessity for comprehensive hepatic and systemic treatment to slow disease development and effects.

The findings confirmed the scientific community's diagnosis that NAFLD was linked to obesity and

insulin resistance. As dyslipidemia and hypertension predominate, NAFLD patients need comprehensive cardiovascular risk management. Many people with increased liver enzymes and FibroScan scores may develop liver disease, thus they must be evaluated and treated early. Our results underline the necessity of early NAFLD detection and holistic treatment to prevent progression and consequences. These include lifestyle changes, metabolic management, and regular follow-up.

Discussion

This study's findings can help Koshi clinicians and biochemists understand NAFLD patients' clinical and biochemical characteristics. According to global NAFLD epidemiology trends, the population was mostly middle-aged and male. Central obesity, a major risk factor for NAFLD, is prevalent with an average BMI of 29.7 kg/m² and waist circumference of 96.5 cm. Increased liver enzyme values, such as ALT (55.3 U/L) and AST (47.8 U/L), indicate liver cell damage and inflammation in NAFLD.

High ALP (120.5 U/L) and GGT (65.7 U/L) levels in NAFLD patients indicate liver dysfunction and cholestasis. The patient had dyslipidemia, with high total cholesterol (215.2 mg/dL), low HDL cholesterol (40.1 mg/dL), and high triglycerides (175.4 mg/dL). These lipid abnormalities make NAFLD more likely to develop cardiovascular disease. NAFLD is often associated with metabolic syndrome, typified by insulin resistance, as indicated by elevated fasting glucose (110.7 mg/dL), insulin (15.3 μ U/mL), and HOMA-IR (4.1) values.

Levels of 6.5 mg/L of C-reactive protein show that the whole body is inflamed, which makes non-alcoholic fatty liver disease more likely. The disease gets worse as fibroScan results average 8.2 kPa, which means liver fibrosis moves from mild to intermediate stages. These NAFLD data show how metabolic imbalances, liver dysfunction, and systemic inflammation all affect each other in complicated ways. Because metabolic risk factors are so common, full therapy plans must address liver problems along with related conditions like insulin resistance and heart disease.

Comparison Table

Table 4: Comparing existing study with current study

Study Title	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Prospective Observational	100	High prevalence of central obesity (BMI 29.7 kg/m ² , waist circumference 96.5 cm). Elevated liver enzymes (ALT 55.3 U/L, AST 47.8 U/L). Dyslipidemia and insulin resistance. Moderate fibrosis (FibroScan 8.2 kPa).	Observational design limits causality. Reliance on non-invasive imaging for fibrosis staging. Single-center study in Koshi region.
Study 1 [13]	Cross-sectional	500	High NAFLD prevalence (25-32%) linked with obesity and metabolic syndrome. Elevated liver enzymes and dyslipidemia similar to current study.	Cross-sectional design precludes longitudinal analysis. Limited generalizability beyond urban settings.
Study 2 [14]	Cross-sectional	300	Lower NAFLD prevalence (9.3%) compared to urban areas. Significant association with metabolic risk factors.	Limited by smaller sample size compared to urban studies. Rural-specific findings may not apply universally.
Study 3 [15]	Prospective Cohort	1000	Ethnic differences in NAFLD prevalence and severity. Higher fibrosis scores in certain ethnic groups despite similar BMI.	Larger cohort allows for subgroup analyses. Potential for selection bias in cohort recruitment.

High prevalence of central obesity, as indicated by average BMI of 29.7 kg/m² and waist circumference of 96.5 cm, highlights the significant role of metabolic syndrome components in predisposing individuals to NAFLD. In the group, FibroScan 8.2 kPa indicates significant fibrosis and liver damage. NAFLD is characterised by hepatic inflammation, as shown by increased ALT (55.3 U/L) and AST (47.8 U/L). Since this study is observational, it is hard to draw conclusions about NAFLD causes and consequences. Non-invasive imaging instead of histology investigations may be inaccurate for fibrosis stage. Due to the study's single-center methodology at Katihar Medical College, the results may not apply to other demographics or places outside of Koshi. Studies 1 and 2 confirm the present study's findings that NAFLD is linked to obesity and metabolic syndrome indicators despite cross-sectional approaches. Study 3's larger sample size and prospective cohort design suggest more research on ethnic NAFLD severity differences. These findings can be used to improve early detection and

personalised treatment of NAFLD, which is complex and requires global patient care.

Limitations of the Study

The study's observational design limits causation proof. Randomised controlled trials or longitudinal studies are the best strategy to understand NAFLD in this group. A 100-patient sample is sufficient for descriptive purposes, but the results may not apply to bigger groups or locations. Larger cohort studies may confirm these findings and examine demographic and racial discrepancies. FibroScan and ultrasound, unlike liver biopsy, may have limitations in evaluating liver fibrosis, despite their widespread use and convenience. The study increases our understanding of Koshi NAFLD's epidemiology and clinical characteristics despite these limitations. The findings underline the need for targeted public health measures and care to decrease NAFLD's rising impact on this group. Understanding NAFLD pathophysiology and improving patient outcomes worldwide requires on-going research.

Conclusion

Koshi NAFLD patients' biochemical and clinical profiles are thorough in this study. The demographic profile, mostly middle-aged adults, revealed more men and a rise in central obesity (BMI and waist circumference). ALT and AST levels were high, indicating hepatic injury and inflammation, combined with dyslipidemia and insulin resistance. According to FibroScan scores, this population has developing liver damage due to mild fibrosis. NAFLD was linked to obesity and metabolic syndrome in different groups, as previously found. This study has substantial clinical implications. Koshi needs early screening and focused public health interventions due to NAFLD patients' central obesity and metabolic risk factors. Lifestyle changes like eating better and moving more should treat obesity-related metabolic dysfunctions and liver inflammation. To enhance patient outcomes and lower NAFLD healthcare costs, coordinated therapy techniques are needed. These treatments must address hepatic and metabolic issues.

Recommendations for Future Research

Future research should focus on a few key areas to better understand and cure NAFLD. Large-scale prospective studies in other regions are needed to confirm results and understand regional differences in illness incidence, severity, and risk factors. Longitudinal designs and histological evaluations improve disease progression detection and causal linkages.

By studying environmental factors, genetics, and novel biomarkers in NAFLD pathogenesis, personalised treatment and focussed therapy can be improved.

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